

Hoda Abd El-Azim*, Sahar F Mehanna and Aisha A Belal

National Institute of Oceanography and Fisheries, Egypt

Dates: Received: 18 February, 2017; Accepted: 09 March, 2017; Published: 13 March, 2017

*Corresponding author: Hoda Abd El-Azim, National Institute of Oceanography and Fisheries, Egypt, Tel: 2012239895; E-mail: Abdelazimh1968@yahoo.com

Keywords: Egypt; Bitter lakes; Striped piggy; Pollution; Water quality; Food availability; Population dynamics; Management

<https://www.peertechz.com>

Research Article

Impacts of Water Quality, Fishing Mortality and Food Availability on the Striped Piggy *Pomadasysstridens* Production in Bitter Lakes, Egypt

Abstract

Pollution, fishing effort and food availability are the main factors affecting the fish production from natural resources. Bitter lakes are one of the important lakes in Egypt that produce a number of commercial species with mean annual fish production of 5000 ton. Recently a dramatic decline in this production is recorded and we try to find the main reasons for this. Water quality of the Bitter lakes and trace elements in the water and fish tissues were investigated during 2013. Five different sampling sites covering the whole course of the Bitter lakes were selected and pH, water temperature and salinity were measured. The cations Ca, Mg, Na, and K concentrations in sample water as well as the heavy metals Cu, Cr, Mn, Pb, and Cd in water and its residues in the tissues of *Pomadasysstridens* were determined. The crustacean communities as one of the main food items for *P. stridens* were studied in the chosen five sites. Density and diversity of marine crustaceans depend not only on the state of pollution but also on the type of substrates and different predators. The distribution of the crustaceans in the Bitter lakes varied widely within the different stations and seasons. A production model was applied to estimate some target reference points for the rational exploitation of *P. stridens* in Bitter lakes. The obtained results revealed that, the production depleting of this species is due to the overfishing and pollution that affect the food availability and the estimated precautionary target reference points advised the reduction of fishing effort by about 40-55% as well as the treatment of pollution resources along the lakes.

Introduction

The aquatic environment with its water quality as well as the over exploitation due to the excessive fishing effort are considered the main factors affecting quality and quantity of fish production either in natural habitats or culture ponds [1,2]. Quality of water may be changed due to different types of chemicals, biological and physical pollutants originating from different industrial and agricultural sources [3]. Pollution of the aquatic environment by inorganic and organic chemicals is a major factor posing serious threat to the survival of aquatic organisms including fish. While, the heavy metals in water considered as the most dangerous source of water pollution [4]. Fish that often exposed to highly polluted water, show different disabilities, ranging from biochemical changes in single cells to changes in the whole organism [5,6]. The toxic effects of heavymetals on fish are multi-directional and manifested by numerous change in the physiological and chemical process of their body system. Accumulation of metals in various organs of fish may cause structural lesions and functional disturbances [7].

Description of the study area

Bitter lakes (30°20' N, 32°23' E) are the largest water bodies along the Suez Canal, containing about 85% of the system's water. The Great and little Bitter lakes [Figure 1], separated by narrows, are saline lakes situated between the north and south parts of the Suez Canal [8]. The Bitter lakes have a surface area of about 250 km². The Bitter Lakes have an important role as a part of very important waterway; Suez Canal, and as a valuable fishing and tourism area in Egypt. Bitter lakes suffer from various sources of pollution, including domestic sewage from the surrounding human settlements, thermal pollution from Abu-Sultan electric power station's cooling water, as well as industrial and agricultural wastes from Ismailia City via the Malaria Drain, which also collects agricultural wastes from the cultivated lands on the west bank of the Great Bitter lake [8]. These activities affect the lakes boundaries and their water quality as well as their fish production.

The grunts, family Haemulidae, consists of 18 genera (133 species), including the population of the striped piggy

Figure 1: Map of the study area.

Pomadasysstridens [9]. The striped piggy is a marine reef-associated species inhabiting the coastal waters of the Indian Ocean; off Red Sea, off South Africa, and off western India and also in Mediterranean Sea as a lessepsian migrant [10]. The striped piggy species is common in the Bitter lakes contributing 4% of the total catch of the lakes. It feeds on zoobenthos especially benthic crustaceans and fishes which are highly sensitive to pollution [11], and their distributions are strongly influenced by the physico-chemical parameters [12].

Extensive research programs have been carried out to investigate the aquatic environment of Bitter lakes [8,13-18]. On the other hand, the studies on the fishery status of different fish stocks inhabiting the lakes are very scarce [19-21]. Different aspects of biological parameters of *P. stridens* have been studied by different authors; Pauly et al. [22], in Philippines waters, Fischer et al. [23], in Mozambique water, Ben-Tuvia and McKay [24], in north-eastern Atlantic and the Mediterranean, Hashemi and Taghavimotlagh [25], in Persian Gulf, Iran.

Since the Bitter lakes represent a most important, vital and strategic region in Suez Canal, which is characterized by highly intensive rate of development, the present work aimed to investigate some physical and chemical parameters of Bitter lakes and to evaluate the pollutants levels including the accumulation of some heavy metals (Cu, Cr, Mn, Pb, and Cd) in the water and the organs of *Pomadasysstridens* as one of the commercial fish species in the lakes. The study aimed also at the estimation of population parameters of this species to evaluate the impact of fishing mortality on its production as well as the investigation of crustacean communities as one of the main food items for it. The results from this study are expected to provide highly important information about how to

manage and develop the fisheries of the region and to improve its water quality.

Materials and Methods

Water quality and metals study

Sampling: Water and fish samples were collected bimonthly from five stations (Defersoir I- Fayed II- Fanarah III – Kabrit IV – Shandorah V) at Bitter lakes during 2013 [Figure 1]. Water samples were collected using Nansen bottles at 30 cm depth, and then stored in acid-washed polyethylene bottles for analysis. All the precautions recommended by Kremling [26] to minimize risks of sample contamination were followed during collection and treatment of samples. Fish samples were dissected and the organs muscles, skin, gills and liver were taken. Each organ was weighed and placed in polyethylene bags according to FAO [27] and UNEP [28], labeled and frozen in deep freezer at a very low freezer temperature (below -20°C) until the time of analysis. Composite samples for small fish samples were taken.

Procedures: At the sampling time, surface water temperature was measured using standard ($0-100^{\circ}\text{C}$) thermometer, pH was measured on the board using a pocket pH meter (Orion 210), while salinity was determined using an inductive salinometer (SCT meters) from yellow springs Instrument Co. model 33. Na, Ca, Mg and K were determined directly after dilution of seawater samples with deionized water by using AAS according to standard methods committee [29].

Solvent extraction was utilized using ammonium pyrrolidinedi-thiocarbamate (APDC) and methyl isobutylketone (MIBK). Watersamples were pre-concentrated with APDC – MIBK extraction procedure according to the standard methods [29]. Heavy metals in the obtained solution were measured using the flame Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer. The preparation of samples of fish to determine concentration of heavy metals was carried out according to FAO [30], and analyzed by flame atomic absorption spectrophotometer. The measurements were performed using Perkin Elmer A Analyst 100 Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer. The obtained data were expressed as $\mu\text{g/g}$ wet weight. Bioaccumulation factor (BAF) was determined according to [31], as: $(\text{BAF}) = C_m / C_{\text{water}}$, where C_m – metal content in the organs (mg kg^{-1}).

Macrobenthic invertebrates study

During the present study five stations were chosen to represent different benthic environments and different conditions in the Bitter lakes and coincide with the water sampling stations. Sub tidal samples were collected from these stations by Van Veen grab with an opening area equal to 0.0288 m^2 of seabed. All samples were gently washed using seawater by 0.75 mm mesh sieve to remove excess sediments, and the remaining portion was fixed in 10% formalin in seawater. Organisms were isolated and identified to species level by Stereo and compound microscopes.

Pomadasys stridens fisheries studies

Sampling: Monthly random samples of *P. stridens* were collected from the local fishermen at Bitter lakes during the period from January 2013 to January 2014. The total length to the nearest millimeter, total weight to the nearest 0.1 g and sex were recorded for each specimen.

Methods: The growth parameters of the von Bertalanffy [32], growth model (K , L_{∞} and t_0) were estimated based on the length frequency distribution by using ELEFANI software [33]. The fitting of the best growth curve was based on the ELEFANI I program [34], which allows the fitted curve through the maximum number of peaks of the length-frequency distribution. With the help of the best growth curve, growth constant (K) and asymptotic length (L_{∞}) were estimated.

The length weight relationship was calculated using the power equation $W=aL^b$, where (a) is constant proportionality and (b) is regression coefficient which were estimated by the least squares regression method.

Total mortality coefficient "Z" is estimated using two different methods; the first is based on the analysis of age composition data (semi-logarithmic regression method of Ricker) [35] and the second is based on the analysis of length composition data (cumulated catch curve method of Jones and Van Zalinge) [36].

Natural mortality coefficient "M" was estimated using the formula suggested by Ursin [37] and Taylor [38], while the fishing mortality coefficient "F" was computed as $F = Z - M$. The exploitation rate "E" was calculated using the formula of Gulland [39], as $E = F/Z$.

Impact of fishing mortality on the striped piggy production

To study the impact of fishing mortality on the production of *P. stridens*, the yield per recruit model of Beverton and Holt (1957) [40] was applied. The formula suggested by Gulland [41] is as follows:

$$Y/R = F e^{-K(Tc-Tr)} W_{\infty} [(1/Z) - (3S/Z+K) + (3S^2/Z+2K) - (S^3/Z+3K)]$$

Where $S = e^{-K(Tc - t_0)}$, K is the von Bertalanffy growth parameter, Tc is the age at first capture, Tr is the age at recruitment, t_0 is the age at which the length is nil, W_{∞} is the asymptotic weight, F is the fishing mortality coefficient, M is the natural mortality coefficient and Z is the total mortality coefficient.

Results and Discussion

Physical and chemical parameters

The physical and chemical parameters with their means and SD for water samples in the selected five sites are given in (Table 1). The average water temperature during the study period varied from a minimum of 22.51°C at station V to a maximum of 24.48°C at station I, which receives cooling water

from the Abu-Sultan electric power station near it. As fish is a cold blooded animal, its body temperature changes according to that of environment affecting its metabolism and physiology and ultimately affecting the production [42]. The average salinity of little Bitter lake was higher than that of Great Bitter lake, with a maximum of 43.96 at station V and a minimum of 43.21 at station I. salinity is a major driving factor that affects the density and growth of aquatic organism's population [43]. The mean pH values of the Bitter lakes ranged from 8.06 at station V to 8.24 at station I. The lowest pH values appeared in site V, where the lake subjected to the increase of sewage wastewater. According to [44], the relatively lowest pH of some sites can be attributed to the discharge of effluents which loaded with a large amount of organic acids.

The mean concentration of calcium for the whole water column ranged from 0.40 g/L at station I to 0.48 g/L at station V. The minimum concentration of magnesium is 1.35 g/L found at station I, while the maximum concentration was 1.49 g/L found at station III. The minimum and maximum concentrations of sodium in surface water were 10.69 g/L at station I, and 12.43 g/L at station V. For potassium, the minimum concentration (0.48 g/L) was recorded at station I, while the maximum concentration (0.56 g/L) was at station V. The high electrolytes content were found at stations V. These can be attributed to the high rate of evaporation, leaching and dissolution of rocks and evaporate deposits at the bottom particularly ultra-basic rocks containing electrolytes ores and station I near the lower salinity at Timsah lake [13,45].

Heavy metals in water

The average concentrations of heavy metals in the different stations of the Bitter lakes (Table 1), (Figure 2), showed annual variations in water samples. The concentrations had the order: $Pb > Cu > Cr > Mn > Cd$. Station V had the higher concentration (0.342, 1.924 and 0.142 µg/L) of Cr, Pb and Cd, respectively. This is may be attributed to the huge amounts of raw sewage, agricultural and industrial wastewater discharged into the south of Bitter lakes from Shandorah dumping drain [1]. Station I had elevated concentrations (0.862 and 0.163 µg/L) of Cu, Mn respectively. Where, it receives a huge amount of industrial pollutant from Abo Sultan power station, agriculture and domestic wastes, as well as the discharges from ships and fishing boats passing or waiting transit through Suez Canal, which contain antifouling paint [46]. The other three stations had lower levels of studied metals because they lie slightly away from the sources of pollution and its effects

Heavy metals in fish

The mean values of the five trace metals (µg g⁻¹wet weight) evaluated in pooled liver, gills, muscle and skin of *P. stridens* collected from Bitter lakes are shown in (Table 2). The distribution of the trace metals varied as follows: Cu and Cd: liver > gill > skin > muscle; Cr: skin > gill > liver > muscle; Mn: gill > skin > liver > muscle; and Pb: gill > liver > skin > muscle. The heavy metal residues in the tissues of *P. stridens* exhibited different patterns of accumulation and distribution among the selected tissues. It was evident from our study that,

Table 1: Some physical and chemical parameters with mean and SD of Bitter lakes water during 2013.

Station Parameter	Defersoior	Fayed	Fanarah	Kabrite	Shandorah
Temperature, °C	24.08 – 24.70	24.02 – 24.64	23.66 – 24.21	23.16 – 23.36	22.38 – 22.61
	24.48 ± 0.350	24.33 ± 0.312	23.94 ± 0.281	23.26 ± 0.101	22.51 ± 0.122
Salinity, ‰	42.77 – 43.69	43.62 – 43.48	43.62 – 43.76	43.36 – 44.34	43.67 – 44.33
	43.21 ± 0.460	43.36 ± 0.100	43.71 ± 0.071	43.83 ± 0.493	43.961 ± 0.33
pH (Unit)	8.221 – 8.270	8.170 – 8.191	8.121 – 8.131	8.061 – 8.092	8.091 – 8.120
	8.242 ± 0.021	8.180 ± 0.011	8.120 ± 0.011	8.071 ± 0.011	8.100 ± 0.022
Ca (g/L)	0.373 – 0.432	0.440 – 0.480	0.451 – 0.551	0.442 – 0.462	0.450 – 0.510
	0.401 ± 0.031	0.460 ± 0.021	0.502 ± 0.051	0.451 ± 0.011	0.480 ± 0.031
Mg (g/L)	1.320 – 1.391	1.430 – 1.490	1.481 – 1.492	1.390 – 1.530	1.431 – 1.491
	1.353 ± 0.041	1.460 ± 0.020	1.491 ± 0.010	1.450 ± 0.091	1.461 ± 0.031
Na (g/L)	10.68 – 10.70	11.73 – 12.19	12.69 – 13.17	11.98 – 12.97	12.15 – 12.71
	10.69 ± 0.011	11.96 ± 0.230	12.93 ± 0.241	12.47 ± 0.486	12.43 ± 0.281
K (g/L)	0.480 – 0.491	0.492 – 0.563	0.522 – 0.541	0.550 – 0.566	0.520 – 0.601
	0.480 ± 0.005	0.521 ± 0.030	0.533 ± 0.010	0.552 – 0.005	0.564 ± 0.040
Cu (µg/L)	0.850 – 0.873	0.669 – 0.692	0.721 – 0.725	0.533 – 0.556	0.610 – 0.636
	0.863 ± 0.110	0.681 ± 0.011	0.723 ± 0.002	0.544 ± 0.012	0.623 ± 0.013
Cr (µg/L)	0.231 – 0.281	0.283 – 0.392	0.250 – 0.263	0.178 – 0.347	0.331 – 0.351
	0.256 ± 0.025	0.337 ± 0.054	0.257 ± 0.007	0.263 ± 0.084	0.342 ± 0.010
Mn (µg/L)	0.160 – 0.167	0.130 – 0.145	0.108 – 0.130	0.079 – 0.114	0.073 – 0.098
	0.163 ± 0.003	0.139 ± 0.007	0.119 ± 0.011	0.108 ± 0.018	0.086 ± 0.012
Pb (µg/L)	1.582 – 2.114	1.603 – 1.976	1.448 – 1.670	1.652 – 1.777	1.880 – 1.968
	1.848 ± 0.260	1.789 ± 0.186	1.559 ± 0.111	1.715 ± 0.062	1.924 ± 0.044
Cd (µg/L)	0.097 – 0.112	0.024 – 0.068	0.059 – 0.097	0.050 – 0.071	0.130 – 0.152
	0.104 ± 0.007	0.046 ± 0.022	0.078 ± 0.070	0.060 ± 0.010	0.142 ± 0.011

liver was the site of maximum accumulation for the elements followed by gills while muscle was the overall site of least metal accumulation. In addition, the liver is the principal organ responsible for the detoxification, transportation, and storage of toxic substances and it is an active site of pathological effects induced by contamination. The gills perform the function of respiration and are directly in contact with water and pollutants that may be present in water. Thus, the concentrations of trace

metals in gills reflect the concentration of trace metals in the waters where the fish lives [47]. The low accumulation of metals in muscle may be due to lack of binding affinity of these metals with the proteins of muscle. This is particularly important because muscles contribute the greatest mass of the flesh that is consumed as food [44]. Except muscles, lead concentration in all organs of studied fish, exceed the permissible limits of WHO, (2 µg/g) according to a report [48]. This shows that these fish could be at risk and who eat it.

The study of bioaccumulation factor (BAF) in aquatic organisms' tissues useful to explain the best organism have the ability of heavy metals bioaccumulation in environment and help to use this organisms as clam in environmental monitoring programs [49].

From the results of bioaccumulation factor obtained in (Table 3) and (Figure 3), it was observed that, it follows the order: $Mn > Cd > Cr > Cu > Pb$ and those metals were accumulated in soft tissue of *P. stridens* by bioaccumulation factor (BAF) as $(0.881, 1.131, 4.190, 0.255, 2.465) \times 10^3$ than concentration in water respectively.

According to Abou-El-Ezz and Abdel-Razeq [50], the concentration of these metals in muscles was much higher ten times in some cases than that found in the surrounding water. This result provide good evidence of metals accumulation in aquatic organisms more than water that help use this organisms as bio-indicators and as a good environmental tools to study of aquatic pollution [51].

Finally, the high level of bioaccumulation factor of Mn, Cd and Cr shows that they were good bio-indicator to monitor pollution in the Bitter lakes for the fish species. Although, we did not investigate the role of adsorption, precipitation of metal ions and influence of interference in this work these will be considered in our next work.

Fishery study

Growth parameters: The present study estimated the asymptotic total length of the combined sexes of *P. stridens* from the Bitter lakes as 23.15 cm TL while the value of K was 0.51 per year and the age at length zero t_0 was -0.29 year. Results indicated that this species have short life and high growth rate especially for young stages. Also, the negative t_0 value means

Figure 2: Level of heavy metals ($\mu\text{g/L}$) in water at different stations along Bitter Lake.

that the juveniles grew more quickly than the predicted growth curve for adults [52].

Length-Weight relationship: The length-weight relationship in fish is of great importance in fishery assessments [53]. Length and weigh relationship in conjunction with age data can give information on the stock composite, age at maturity, life span, mortality, growth and production. Length-weight relationship of *P. stridens* in the Bitter lakes was fitted for data of the all individuals combined (Figure 4). The total length varied from 7 to 19.9 cm while the total weight ranged between 4.9 and 121 g and the resultant equation was: $W = 0.0143 L^{2.9794}$.

Isometric growth was observed for striped piggy in Bitter lakes as the value of b was not significantly different from 3 (95% Confidence Interval = 2.9236 - 3.0353). The same finding was recorded in Hashemi and Taghavimotlagh [25], where they gave $b = 3.04$ and the growth pattern was isometric in the Persian Gulf. The value of b for Philippines waters was estimated as 3 for both sexes [22]. The variation of b in the different regions could be due to the seasonal fluctuations in environmental parameters, physiological conditions of the fish at the time of collection, sex, gonad development and nutritive conditions in the environment of fish [54].

Mortality Coefficients: The obtained results (Figure 5) indicate that the estimated values of total mortality coefficient Z from the two different methods are very close to each other with a geometric mean of 1.28/year. The mean value of natural mortality coefficient M was computed as 0.40/year and accordingly the fishing mortality coefficient F was estimated as 0.88 yearly. The exploitation ratio of striped piggy in Bitter lakes was found to be very high (0.69/year) compared to the optimum values given by Gulland [39] and Pauly [33] indicating the high level of exploitation.

Optimum length, Length at first capture and length at maturity: The estimated optimum length L_{opt} for striped piggy in the Bitter lakes was 18.35 cm TL, while the length at first capture L_c was 10.75 cm and the length at first maturity L_m was 15.11 cm. It was found that up to 95% of the striped piggy catch was under the optimum size and up to 85% was not reaching its sexual maturity (Figure 6).

Feeding habits: Analysis of full stomachs revealed that the striped piggy is a carnivorous species, fed mainly on crustaceans (62.12%), mollusks (20.31%) small fishes (11.31%), polychaets (1.26%), while the detritus and digested food constituted 5%.

Impact of fishing mortality: The model of Beverton and Holt [40], which was based on the estimation of the yield per

Table 2: Heavy metals concentration ($\mu\text{g/g}$) with mean and SD of different organs of *Pomadasystridens* collected from Bitter lakes during 2013.

Heavy metal	Organs			
	Muscles	Skin	Gills	Liver
Cu	0.518 - 0.6930.605 ± 0.016	1.281 - 2.6841.877 ± 0.24	1.896 - 1.9861.923 ± 0.021	3.621 - 5.3824.482 ± 0.024
Cr	0.334 - 0.4350.329 ± 0.02	1.262 - 1.789 1.461 ± 0.15	1.074 - 1.5081.231 ± 0.56	0.773 - 0.7950.784 ± 0.02
Mn	0.495 - 0.5320.507 ± 0.06	14.25 - 19.6516.95 ± 4.11	16.86 - 20.5018.68 ± 2.89	12.36 - 12.9612.47 ± 4.36
Pb	0.336 - 0.5660.451 ± 0.03	3.282 - 5.3564.360 ± 0.51	6.376 - 7.8436.961 ± 0.18	5.754 - 7.2416.497 ± 0.41
Cd	0.200 - 0.2250.212 ± 0.16	0.487 - 1.1610.808 ± 0.12	0.635 - 1.1790.863 ± 0.11	0.866 - 1.5481.207 ± 0.12

recruit under a particular set of fishing mortality coefficients, was applied. The input parameters used in Beverton and Holt model are as follows:

$L_{\infty} = 23.15$ cm, $W_{\infty} = 166.3$ g, $K = 0.51$ yr⁻¹, $M = 0.4$ yr⁻¹, $F =$ variable, $T_r = 0.42$ yr

$T_c =$ variable, $t_0 = -0.29$ yr and $Z = 1.28$ yr⁻¹

Table 3: Bioaccumulation factor x 103 (BAF) for metals in *Pomadasysstridens*'s tissues.

Heavy metal	Organs			
	Muscles	Skin	Gills	Liver
Cu	0.881	2.732	2.799	6.525
Cr	1.131	5.024	4.233	2.696
Mn	4.190	140.1	154.3	103.1
Pb	0.255	2.467	3.939	3.676
Cd	2.465	9.395	10.03	14.03

Figure 3: Heavy metal concentrations in water, bioaccumulation in fish muscles and bioaccumulation factors.

Figure 4: Length weight relationship of striped piggy from Bitter lakes.

Figure 5: Cumulated catch curve of striped piggy from Bitter lakes.

The estimated yield per recruit of *P. stridens* in the Bitter lakes (Figure 7), indicates that, the yield per recruit was zero when the fishing mortality was zero, then the yield per recruit increases rapidly as the fishing mortality increases and reaches its maximum value at fishing mortality coefficient of 0.7 after which the yield per recruit decreases with further increase of fishing mortality. The results indicate also that, at the present level of fishing mortality coefficient ($F = 0.88$), age at first capture ($T_c = 0.92$ year) and natural mortality coefficient ($M = 0.40$), the yield per recruit was estimated to be 24.16 g. This means that, the present level of fishing mortality is higher than that which gives the maximum yield per recruit and to obtain the maximum yield per recruit, the fishing mortality coefficient must be reduced from 0.88 to 0.7 (21%).

To show the impact of mesh size on the striped piggy production, the yield per recruit was estimated using two different T_c values (0.5 and 1.5 year). The results (Figure 7), indicated that the Y/R increases with the increase of mesh sizes

Pomadasys stridens food availability

Distribution of macrobenthic invertebrates in the Bitter lakes: *Pomadasys stridens* feed on crustaceans, mollusks, small fishes & polychaetes. And show variation in relation to different size groups, seasons and environmental biota [55]. The annual changes of macrobenthic invertebrate community in Bitter lakes from (summer, 2013 to spring, 2014) comprised 36 species affiliating to 6 phyla. Polychaeta (15 species and 6689 animals / m²), Mollusca (10 species and 132244 animals / m²), Crustacea (6 species and 5767 animals / m²), Echinodermata (3 species and 623 animals / m²), Cephalochordata (one species and 1736 animals / m²) and Pripulida (one species and 35 animals / m²). Figure 8 shows the seasonal variation of crustaceans where it recorded only 6 species and 5767 animals / m². This low density of crustaceans is mainly due to high pollution of the Bitter lakes.

Descriptive analysis and spatial variation: The distribution of the crustaceans in the Bitter lakes varied widely within the different stations (Figure 9). The highest crustacean species number and density was recorded at stations II and III (4 and 3 species, respectively) and (1146 and 1145 animals / m², respectively). The highest density at station II was attributed to *Balanus* sp. Which constituting 15% of the total crustaceans at the Bitter lakes with an annual average of 868 animals / m². Stations I and IV come in the second degree where the density and species number were 2 and 1 species for each and 277 and 35 animals / m², respectively. As a result of pollution, the crustaceans at station V were totally missing throughout this investigation.

Seasonal variation: The distribution of the crustaceans in the Bitter lakes varied widely within the different seasons (Figure 10). Autumn and winter seasons encompassed the highest density (1979 and 3164 animals / m², respectively) and the highest number of species (4 species for each, respectively) as well. Otherwise summer and spring recorded the lowest population density (174 and 450 animals / m², respectively) and the lowest number of species (3 and 4 species, respectively).

Figure 6: Critical lengths of striped piggy from Bitter lakes.

Figure 7: Yield per recruit analysis of *P. stridens* from Bitter lakes.

Figure 9: Spatial variation of crustacean community (animals / m²) at the different stations in Bitter lakes

Figure 8: Population density of benthic fauna (animals / m²) from Bitter lakes.

Conclusion and Recommendations

It could be concluded that both of pollution and excessive fishing mortality are responsible for the severe reduction in the fish production from Bitter lakes. Pollution affected the water and fish quality and alters the physical and chemical characters of its aquatic environment. Also, pollution leads to the decreasing the natural main food of the species where crustaceans are very sensitive to pollution. While the high fishing effort causes both growth and recruitment overfishing where all large sized specimens are disappeared from the fishery and the striped piggy catch decreased to less than its half value. So it recommended that preventing all kinds of pollutants to keep the quality of water, reducing the fishing effort by at least 40% of its current level, banning all kinds of illegal fishing methods and reviewing the fisheries and environmental laws.

Figure 10: Seasonal average of crustacean community (animals /m²) in Bitter lakes.

References

- Saeed SM, Shaker IM (2008) Assessment of heavy metals pollution in water and sediments and their effect on *Oreochromis niloticus* in the Northern Delta lakes, EGYPT. 8th International Symposium on Tilapia in Aquaculture. [Link: https://goo.gl/6FL3IS](https://goo.gl/6FL3IS)
- Mehanna SF (2008) Northern Delta Lakes, Egypt: constraints and challenges. *Tropentag* 7–9. [Link: https://goo.gl/oeWsqf](https://goo.gl/oeWsqf)
- Andhale AV, Zambare SP (2012) Effect of nickel induced respiratory alterations in freshwater bivalve *Lamallidens marginalis*. *Int. Multidiscip. Res J* 2: 01-03. [Link: https://goo.gl/sLxXUS](https://goo.gl/sLxXUS)
- El-Wakil HF, Seehy MA, El-Dahhar AA, Ibrahim MM, Hemeida AA et al. (2008) The Effect of Environmental Condition on Genetic Background in Nile Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*). *J Arab Aquac Soc* 5: 101-118. [Link: https://goo.gl/l55sdJ](https://goo.gl/l55sdJ)
- Velcheva I, Tomova E, Arnaudova D, Arnaudov A (2010) Morphological investigation on gills and liver of freshwater fish from DAM Lake "Studen Kladenets". *Bulgarian Journal of Agricultural Science* 16: 364-368. [Link: https://goo.gl/oy07U5](https://goo.gl/oy07U5)
- Bernet D, Schmidt H, Meier W, Burkhardt-Holm P, Wahli T (1999) Histopathology in fish: proposal for a protocol to assess aquatic pollution. *J Fish Dis* 22: 25-34. [Link: https://goo.gl/mT5p4e](https://goo.gl/mT5p4e)
- Emere MC, Dibal DM (2013) Metal Accumulation in Some Tissues/Organs of a Fresh Water Fish (*Clarias Gariepinus*) from Some Polluted Zones of River Kaduna. *Journal of Biology, Agriculture and Healthcare* 3: 1. [Link: https://goo.gl/kMJ2S6](https://goo.gl/kMJ2S6)
- El-Bassat RA (2008) Composition and abundance of the zooplankton community in the Bitter lakes, Egypt, in relation to environmental factors. *African Journal of Aquatic Science* 33: 233–240 [Link: https://goo.gl/5Y0mmd](https://goo.gl/5Y0mmd)
- Nelson JS (1994) *Fishes of the world*. Third edition. John Wiley & Sons, Inc., New York. 600.
- Golani DL, Orsi Relini L, Massuti E, Quignard JP (2002) *CIESM Atlas of Exotic Species in the Mediterranean*. Vol. 1. Fishes. F. Briand (ed.). 256p. CIESM Publishers, Monaco. [Link: https://goo.gl/MCj6kk](https://goo.gl/MCj6kk)
- Guerra-Garcia JM, Garcia-Gomez JC (2004) Crustacean assemblages and sediment pollution in an exceptional case study: A harbour with two opposing entrances. *Crustaceana* 77: 353-370 [Link: https://goo.gl/fl1N8p](https://goo.gl/fl1N8p)
- Varadarajan D, Soundarapandian P, Pushparajan N (2013) Effect of Physico-Chemical Parameters on Crabs Biodiversity. *J Marine Sci Res Dev* 3: 1 [Link: https://goo.gl/QmL0YM](https://goo.gl/QmL0YM)
- Abd El-Azim H (2002) Heavy metals in Suez Canal relevant to land based sources. Ph. D. Thesis, Fac. Sci., El-Mansoura Univ [Link: https://goo.gl/JAgxp7](https://goo.gl/JAgxp7)
- Abd El-Azim H, El-Moselhy M (2005) Determination and partitioning of metals in sediments along the Suez Canal by sequential extraction. *J Mar Sys* 56: 363-374. [Link: https://goo.gl/lnDCDQ](https://goo.gl/lnDCDQ)
- El-Moselhy KHM (2006) Bioaccumulation of Mercury in some marine organisms from Lake Timsah and Bitter lakes (Suez Canal, Egypt). *Egyptian Journal of Aquatic Research* 32: 124-134 [Link: https://goo.gl/F2vN8p](https://goo.gl/F2vN8p)
- Amer A, Abd El-Azim H (2007) Levels of trace metals in marine macroalgae from Bitter Lakes, Suez Canal, Egypt. *Egypt J of Aquat Biol And Fish* 11: 191–205.
- Hamed MA, El-Sawy MA, Abu El-Naga EH (2012) Hydrochemistry and nutrients of Bitter and Tamsah Lakes, Suez Canal, Egypt. *Egypt J Aquat Biol & Fish* 16: 1–12 [Link: https://goo.gl/Bk3R6Y](https://goo.gl/Bk3R6Y)
- Ahmed S, Kaiser MF (2014) Geo-Environmental Assessment of the Suez Canal Area, using remote sensing and GIS Techniques. *Journal of Earth Sciences and Geotechnical Engineering* 4: 69-78 [Link: https://goo.gl/632rY8](https://goo.gl/632rY8)
- Mehanna SF (2004) Population dynamics of keeled mullet, *Liza carinata* and golden grey mullet, *Liza aurata* at the Bitter Lakes, Egypt. *Bull. Nat. Inst. Oceanogr. Fish ARE* 30: 315-321 [Link: https://goo.gl/FRf5J2](https://goo.gl/FRf5J2)
- Mehanna SF (2005) Stock assessment of the blue swimmer crab *Portunus pelagicus* (Linnaeus, 1766) at the Bitter Lakes, Suez Canal, Egypt. *Egypt J Aquat. Biol & Fis* 9: 187-213. [Link: https://goo.gl/c3mRp1](https://goo.gl/c3mRp1)
- Mehanna SF, El-Gammal FI (2007) Population characteristics and reproductive dynamics of the thinlip mullet *Liza ramada* (Risso, 1810) at Suez Canal Lakes, Egypt. *Egypt J Aquat Biol Fish* 11: 307-324.
- Pauly D R, Froese, J S Albert (1998). The BRAINS table. p. 195-198. In R. Froese and D. Pauly (eds.) *FishBase 98: concepts, design and data sources*. ICLARM, Manila, Philippines. 298 p.
- Fischer WI, Sousa C, Silva A, Freitas JM, Poutiers W, et al. (1990). *Fichas FAO de identificação de espécies para actividades de pesca*. Guia de campo das espécies comerciais marinhas e de águas salobras de Moçambique. Publicação preparada em colaboração com o Instituto de Investigação Pesqueira de Moçambique, com financiamento do Projecto PNUD/FAO MOZ/86/030 e de NORAD. Roma FAO 424. [Link: https://goo.gl/EUzrix](https://goo.gl/EUzrix)
- Ben-Tuvia A, McKay R (1986) *Haemulidae*. p. 858-864. In P.J.P. Whitehead, M.-L. Bauchot, J.-C. Hureau, J. Nielsen and E. Tortonese (eds.) *Fishes of the north-eastern Atlantic and the Mediterranean*. volume 2. UNESCO, Paris.
- Hashemi AA, Taghavi-motlagh SA (2012) Population Parameters and Length-Weight relationship of striped piggy (*Pomadys stridens*) in northwest of Persian Gulf (Khuzestan Coastal Waters, Iran). *Journal of Novel Applied Sciences* 1: 57-62. [Link: https://goo.gl/440Nid](https://goo.gl/440Nid)
- Kremling K (1983) Trace metals fronts in European shelf waters. *Nature* 303: 225-227. [Link: https://goo.gl/YmnCUK](https://goo.gl/YmnCUK)
- Food and Agriculture Organization, FAO (1983) *Manual of methods in aquatic environment research part 9. Analysis of metals and organochlorines*, FAO Fish. Tech 121 [Link: https://goo.gl/kM06mR](https://goo.gl/kM06mR)
- United Nations Environment programme UNEP (1984). *Sampling of selected marine organisms and sample preparation of trace metals analysis*

- Reference Methods for Marine Pollution Studies (UNEP). no. 7(rev.2). [Link: https://goo.gl/aIKLwS](https://goo.gl/aIKLwS)
29. American Public Health Association APHA (1989). Standard methods for the examination of water and wastewater, part 3, determination of metals, 17thed. Washington, D. C.: American Public Health Association, American Water Works Association and Water Pollution Control Federation 164 [Link: https://goo.gl/xXzFke](https://goo.gl/xXzFke)
 30. Food and Agriculture Organization FAO (1976) Manual of methods in aquatic environment research part 3.Sampling and analysis of biological material, FAO Fish. Tech Pap No 158. [Link: https://goo.gl/3uQ0bE](https://goo.gl/3uQ0bE)
 31. Demina LL, Galkin SV, Shumilin EN (2009) Bioaccumulation of some trace elements in the biota of hydrothermal fields of the Guaymas Basin (Gulf of California). Boletín De LA Sociaeded Geologica Mexicana 61: 31-45. [Link: https://goo.gl/1ISyVp](https://goo.gl/1ISyVp)
 32. Bertalanffy von L (1938) A quantitative theory of organic growth (Inquiries on growth laws. 2). Hum Biol 10: 181-213 [Link: https://goo.gl/VhJ9ZF](https://goo.gl/VhJ9ZF)
 33. Pauly D (1987) A review of the ELEFAN system for analysis of length-frequency data in fish and aquatic invertebrates. Length-based methods in fisheries reseatch 13: 7-34. [Link: https://goo.gl/E4Nvzq](https://goo.gl/E4Nvzq)
 34. Pauly D, David N (1981) ELEFAN-I a basic program for the objective extraction of growth parameters from Length frequency data. Meeresforschung / Rep Mar Res 28: 205-211. [Link: https://goo.gl/FPYGuC](https://goo.gl/FPYGuC)
 35. Ricker WE (1975) Computation and interpretation of biological statistics of fish population. Bull Fish Res Bd Can 191: 382. [Link: https://goo.gl/QEtFBP](https://goo.gl/QEtFBP)
 36. Jones R, Van Zalinge NP (1981) Estimates of mortality rate and population size for shrimp in Kuwait waters. Kuwait Bull Mar Sci 2: 273-288.
 37. Ursin E (1967) A mathematical model of some aspects of fish growth, respiration and mortality. J Fish Res Bd Can 24: 2355-2453. [Link: https://goo.gl/BtgXFD](https://goo.gl/BtgXFD)
 38. Taylor CC (1960) Temperature, growth and mortality – the Pacific cockle. J Cons CIEM 26: 117-124. [Link: https://goo.gl/EfpPWn](https://goo.gl/EfpPWn)
 39. Gulland JA (1971) The Fish Resources of the Ocean. Fishing News (Books), Ltd., for FAO 255. [Link: https://goo.gl/Am7eej](https://goo.gl/Am7eej)
 40. Beverton RJH, Holt SJ (1957) On the dynamics of exploited fish population. UK Min Agr Fish. Food Ish. Invest 19: 533. [Link: https://goo.gl/51rcgc](https://goo.gl/51rcgc)
 41. GulaInd, JA (1969) Manual of methods for fish stock assessment. Part (1). Fish population analysis. FAO Manual Fish. Sci 4:154. [Link: https://goo.gl/CNLRsN](https://goo.gl/CNLRsN)
 42. Bhatnagar A, Devi P (2013). Water quality guidelines for the management of pond fish culture. International Journal of Environmental Sciences 3: 6 [Link: https://goo.gl/jjb13b](https://goo.gl/jjb13b)
 43. Jamabo NA (2008) Ecology of *Tympanotonus fuscatus* (Linnaeus, 1758) in the Mangrove Swamps of the Upper Bonny River, Niger Delta, Nigeria. Ph.D. Thesis, Rivers State University of Science and Technology, Port Harcourt, Nigeria, pp 231
 44. Osman AGM, Kloas W (2010) Water Quality and Heavy Metal Monitoring in Water, Sediments, and Tissues of the African Catfish *Clarias gariepinus* (Burchell, 1822) from the River Nile, Egypt. Journal of Environmental Protection 1: 389-400. [Link: https://goo.gl/sNs66b](https://goo.gl/sNs66b)
 45. Ramollo PP (2008). Bio assessing the impact water quality on the health and parasite composition of *Oreochromis Mossambicus* at the Phalaborwa industrial complex (PIC) and the Barrage (Olifants River) in the Limpopo province South Africa. Msc Thesis Faculty of Science and Agriculture. University of Limpopo, Sovenga, South Africa [Link: https://goo.gl/TsABVo](https://goo.gl/TsABVo)
 46. Soliman Y, Abd El-Azim H, El-Sawy M A (2010). Copper emission loading from antifouling paints and their relation to industrials and waste water effluents to the Suez bay transit area. Egyptian Journal of Aquatic research. 36: 2 [Link: https://goo.gl/J0Vu0N](https://goo.gl/J0Vu0N)
 47. Romeo M, Siau Y, Sidoumou Z, Gnassia-Barelli M (1999) Heavy metal distribution in different fish species from the Mauritania coast. The Science of the Total Environment. 232: 169-175. [Link: https://goo.gl/WgW8Jr](https://goo.gl/WgW8Jr)
 48. Food and Agriculture Organization FAO (1992) Committee for inland fisheries of Africa. Report of the third session of the working party on pollution and fisheries. FAO Fisheries report. No. 471. [Link: https://goo.gl/juuwJH](https://goo.gl/juuwJH)
 49. Rainbow PS (2007). Trace metal bioaccumulation: Models, metabolic availability and toxicity. Environment International 33: 576-582 [Link: https://goo.gl/cEz0kC](https://goo.gl/cEz0kC)
 50. Abou-El-Ezz, AS, Abdel-Razeq S (1991) "Heavy Metals Accumulation in the Tilapia *Nilotica* L., and in the Water of Lake EL-Manzalah," Egyptian Journal of Applied Science 6: 37-52.
 51. Hedouim L, Pringault O, Metian M, Bustamante P, Warnau M (2007) Nickel bioaccumulation in Bivalves from the New Caledonia Lagoon: Sea water and food Exposure. Chemosphere 66: 1449-1457 [Link: https://goo.gl/euDUC4](https://goo.gl/euDUC4)
 52. King M (2007) Fisheries biology & assessment and management. Fishing news press 340. [Link: https://goo.gl/ZQ2cPg](https://goo.gl/ZQ2cPg)
 53. Haimovici M, Velasco G (2000) Length Weight relationship of marine from southern Brazil. NAGA 23: 14-16. [Link: https://goo.gl/DWYfs5](https://goo.gl/DWYfs5)
 54. Biswas SP (1993) Manuel of methods in fish biology, fish biology & Ecology laboratory, Dibrugarh university, Dibrugarh: 157.
 55. Amtyaz Safi, Atiqullah Khan M, Zaheer Khan M, Usman Ali Hashmi M (2013) Observations on the Food and Feeding Habits of Striped piggy, *Pomadasysstridens* (Forsskal, 1775) (Family; Pomadasyidae) from Karachi Coast, Pakistan. International Journal of Fauna and Biological Studies 1: 7-14. [Link: https://goo.gl/7cQ85l](https://goo.gl/7cQ85l)